

Advanced Textile Composite External Fixator Ring

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SUMMARY: Current work reports the design and evaluation of circular rings for Ilizarov external fixator system. A radiolucent composite material of knitted aramid fibre (and short chopped carbon) and epoxy resin is used to replace stainless steel, currently the most commonly used material. The use of a radiolucent composite material permits easier and more accurate radiographic evaluation of the healing process, and results in a much lighter system. The half ring was modelled by the Finite Element Method (FEM) for the worst possible in service loading condition. Prototype of the half ring is produced using two different fabrics. Knitted fibre (Kevlar-29) and short chopped carbon fibre is used as reinforcement of the epoxy resin matrix. In-plane compressive strength and stiffness were tested according to the ASTM specification. The performance was evaluated and compared to an existing system in simulated in service conditions.

KEYWORDS: Ilizarov external fixator, Finite Element Method (FEM), Radiolucency, Knitted and short chopped fabric, Kevlar and Carbon fiber, In-Plane Compressive strength

INTRODUCTION:

External fixators are used in the treatment of fracture where conservative reduction and treatment (for example, with a plaster cast) would prove insufficient, as well as in the rectification of defects and limb lengthening. In 1951, with hand made equipment, Ilizarov developed a special circular fixation device for the treatment of bone defects and non-unions or for limb lengthening. Today Ilizarov's methods [1] are an well-accepted means of correction of severe orthopedic deformities. Limb correction is a gradual process which not only lengthens and straightens bone but also angulate or rotate the position of bone and soft tissue so a limb can function as normally as possible [2]. The apparatus (*Fig. 1*) designed by Ilizarov consists of a number of standardized interchangeable components, which make it very versatile. Transfix wires or Kirschner wires, 1.5mm or 1.8mm in diameter, are used to transfix the bone. The wires are attached to external rings and tensioned. The tension applied is usually in the range of 90kg-130kg[2], [3]. The wires are fixed to the rings with bolts. Threaded rods and nuts or telescoping rods and nuts are used to connect the rings to each other. The rings are a vital part of the system.

Current materials used in the production of the Ilizarov external fixator ring are stainless steel, titanium or aluminium, which are radio-opaque (Fig2). The rings and supports may obscure the healing

Fig1: Schematic Diagram of Ilizarov external Fixator

Fig2: radiograph of a Stainless Steel System

bone, hindering evaluation of progress. Use of radiolucent composite material will help to overcome this problem. In order to achieve the required stiffness in the ring, it will be necessary to create more cumbersome components, the overall weight of the system will be reduced due to the lower density of the fibre composite material. The principal objective of this work is to replace the existing material satisfactorily with a composite material.

METHOD:

Two stages were necessary to achieve satisfactory replacement of the stainless steel material of the ring with a radiolucent material. The first stage involved FEM modeling of the external fixator ring. In the second stage, a series of prototypes was produced and mechanical testing of the prototype was performed to support the analytical work.

The ring has been designed to withstand the worst possible loading condition so that it can be readily used for the other load conditions. Depending on the bone position and the crossing angle of the Kirschner wire the load cases are defined. Four different loading cases (Fig: 3) are analyzed for three different ring sizes (Ring Radius of 40, 70 and 100mm):

1. Centre-90, 2. Centre-angle, 3. Offset-90 and 4. Offset-angle

Fig3: Different Analyzed Load cases

FEM Modeling:

Geometry:

A Pseudo 3-D model is created using finite element (FE) meshed model, with a total of 2592 2-D solid elements for a circular ring. The model is generated using Patran (McNeill Schwindler Corporation) [4], a Finite Element software package. Four noded quadrilateral 2-D solid elements are used to create the model. The software checks the model before analysis to ensure element edge angles and element faces are within 45-135° range, except at locations where the errors are not significant and will not significantly affect the overall stress distribution. The circular ring has inner radius of 100mm. The stainless steel ring has a cross sectional width of 14mm and thickness of 4mm.

Boundary Conditions:

In an actual Ilizarov external fixator the rings are assembled to build a supporting frame with the help of vertical supporting rods and Kirschner wires. Typically, the bone force is carried by 3 or 4 crossed Kirschner wires, 1.5mm or 1.8mm in diameter. When the ring is in use there should not be any motion in the direction of bone axis. In the model, movement in the Z direction is restricted at the points where the vertical supports are connected. At one support the nodes have been constrained with no translational motion in the X, Y and Z direction. Two other supports are modeled, with the nodes on the model in the areas constrained in the Z direction (disp=0). No rotational constraint is applied to the movement of the supporting sections.

Loads:

Tensions in the wires in the model were in accordance with the guidelines for surgeons given by Golyakovosky and Frankel [5]. The tension in the wires in the model is 80 Kg (784N). According to the biomechanical calculations of Pauwels [6], the force carried by the femur is three times the body weight, in this study a body weight of 70kg is used. The loading in the Z direction (along the axis of the bone) is calculated according to the relation:
$$F_{z,a} = \frac{T_a}{\sum_n T_n} \left(\frac{3W}{2} \right),$$

where N is the number of wires carrying the total load, T_a is the tension in the wire a in the non-weight bearing phase, and W is the body weight (in Newton) of the patient.

Material Properties:

The most commonly used materials for Ilizarov external fixators are Stainless steel and Aluminium. Standard values for the mechanical properties of stainless steel ($E=210$ Gpa, $\nu=0.31$) are used [7].

Analysis:

The stresses in the system are assessed using Von Mises' equivalent stress, calculated according to the Von Mises' yield Criterion, given by: $2\sigma_{vm}^2 = (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2$ where $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are the principal stresses at any point in the system; stresses in the x, y and z axes of the model ($\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz}$); and the maximum shear stress. The Z-axis defined to be the

perpendicular to the plane of the ring (the x-y plane). Stress analysis is done using ABAQUS/Post [8]. Fig: 4 show a contour plot of the stresses in the Ilizarov ring. The stresses are concentrated around the holes adjacent to the offset carrying the wire.

Fig: 4 Von-Mises stresses plotted on FEM model

Result shows increasing trend of stresses with the increasing of ring size. Maximum stress (Graph1) was found for 100mm-radius ring as high as 230 MPa while for 40mm ring its only 94.58 MPa. Ring size also has tremendous effect on overall stiffness of the system, as its clear from Graph2. Wire crossing angles were found to influence the system a lot. Crossing the wire at an angle applies uneven forces to the rings; thus the deformation may be responsible for high stress

Graph 1: Comparative Von Mises' stress Graph2: Deformation of rings for different load cases

Model shows the expected high levels of stresses in the Ilizarov ring, and localized yielding is noticed at high stress position. Bigger ring size results in a higher stress condition, which cause high deformation. Higher stresses were found for eccentric bone position and wires crossing at angle. Deformation also is higher than other load cases. From the results it may be concluded that the worst load case is that where the bone is not in at the center of the ring and wires are crossing at acute angle. Only this case is considered for the designing of a novel ring fixator system.

Redesign of the ring:

The fixator ring is redesigned using comparative studies of material properties as a basis. In order to achieve this objective, the bending stiffness (EI) values must be equivalent. To replace the existing radio opaque stainless steel material satisfactorily with a radiolucent and lighter composite material, matching of the stiffness is the most suitable method [9]. The design must satisfy the requirements that the stress is well below the yield criterion and deformation should be less than 1% of the nominal diameter.

$$(EI)_{\text{stainless-steel}} = (EI)_{\text{composite}}, \text{ for the cross section } I = tw^3/12$$

Where w =width of the ring

t =thickness of the ring.

$$\text{which leads to } \frac{(tw^3)_{ss}}{(tw^3)_{comp}} = \frac{E_{ss}}{E_{comp}} \quad (1)$$

This analysis gives the approximate dimensions, which are required to make the composite ring from the above relation. Now validity of the dimensional change is checked using another finite element model, where fiber reinforced materials was analyzed. Two different fiber reinforcements were of aramid (Kevlar-29) and carbon fiber is used [10].

Experimental work:

Verification of material properties:

Flat knitted composite panels were produced and tested (according to ASTM standard [11]) to verify on the elastic properties used for the FEM analysis. Knitted Kevlar -29 fibre was used as

Graph 3: Tensile test result for Flat Knitted Kevlar Composite

reinforcement of Epoxy matrix. Panels were post-cured at a temperature of 80°C for 8 hrs. INSTRON-8516 machine is used for the tensile tests. Results (*Graph3*) are shown below:

- Tensile strength = **114 MPa** (110 ~ 121MPa)
- Tensile modulus = **8.79 GPa** (8.23 ~ 9.40Gpa)

- Fracture strain = **3.51%** (3.34 ~ 3.83%)

Producing the prototype:

Ring prototype was fabricated using a three-piece steel mould with a hand lay up process. Two different fabrics were used as reinforcement of Epoxy matrix (Chemcrete R-50 resin and H-64 hardener) for the ring prototype. Knitted Kevlar-29 fabric and short chopped Carbon fibre was the reinforcement for the composite. Typically short chopped fibers length was 10-12mm.

Fig.5 Comparative Radiograph

Post curing of the prototype was done at a temperature of 80°C for 8 hrs. Comparative study on radiolucency was done for three different materials. Composite ring showed much better result compared to metal rings as Stainless Steel or Aluminium (*Fig.5*).

Mechanical testing:

In plane compressive strength for the ring will be done according to ASTM specification [12]. This test method is used to measure the compressive strength and stiffness of circular ring elements of external fixators, when loaded in the plane of the ring. The results obtained in this test method are not intended to predict the clinical efficacy or safety of the tested products. This test method is intended only to measure the uniformity of the product tested or to compare the mechanical properties of different products. Test set up is shown below (*Fig 6*). INSTRON-8516 Machine is used for the testing.

Fig 6: Test setup for in-plane compressive strength test

Results:

Comparative in-plane compressive stiffness is determined for short-chopped carbon fiber and knitted kevlar composite ring. The graph (Graph 3) shows the test result.

Graph 3: Test result from the In-plane Compressive test

In-plane Properties	Short-chopped Carbon fiber	Knitted Kevlar fiber
Compressive Stiffness (N/mm)	96.34	36.477
Compressive Yield Strength (N)	1135	560
Maximum Compressive strength (N)	1400	560

Table1: Summary of the mechanical test result

CONCLUSIONS:

Radiographic analysis confirms the radiolucency of both knitted kevlar and short-chopped carbon fiber composite. Carbon fiber showed better performance in the radiographic analysis.

From the results of the mechanical test it can be concluded that short chopped carbon fiber shows much superiority in properties than knitted aramid fiber (Kevlar-29). So, for specific application as in Ilizarov external fixator ring carbon fiber composite is superior to knitted kevlar. With superior properties in mechanical and radiographic short-chopped carbon fiber has tremendous potential to satisfactorily replace the radio opaque metal components in Ilizarov external fixator system.

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